

Contextual Appraisal of Education, Women and the Dynamics of National Development: The Reminiscence of Nigeria

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Abstract

Development in every nation is solely rested on the educational attainment of its citizens; because they are the instrument and drivers of development. Since the creation, a woman has been a partner to the first man, to help him in the process of his survival and progress that could be achieved. Women are regarded as essential beings in providing support for men; adequate attention is therefore expected to be accorded the one providing the support, so as to ensure that quality and positive types of support are received. The needs of women must therefore be catered for, especially in their educational attainment, for the best impact on the growth and development of the individual and the society. The task of this paper is to look at the educational attainment of the Nigerian women and the consequential impact on national development. For clarity purpose, the paper analyzed the connection between education and national development vis-a-viz the concern for women, their education and the contributions being made to salvage the situations themselves. The study further examined the impact of women education in the development of a nation, revealing how wives of the Nigerian governors (first ladies) have been using their educatedness in the political offices occupied to improve the situations for girls, women and other vulnerable individuals, including children. The researchers were motivated to expatiate on the various patterns of women's contributions to national development and the numerous factors hindering women education were also not ignored. This paper concluded by recognizing the positive results and changes that have occurred in the educational attainment of women in Nigeria. It recommended that adequate measures be taken in promoting women education in Nigeria, so as to be the vanguard and enablers of development and remain very relevant in the Nigeria's development process.

Keywords: *Contextual Appraisal, Education, Women, National Development and Reminiscence.*

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Introduction

The strength of every nation is in the type and quality of education provided for its citizens, perhaps, prompting Fafunwa (1971:3) to see education as one of the major concerns of man throughout ages. In the old Africa, before the introduction of Western education, the traditional (indigenous) education had a guiding principle with the main purpose of functionalism, that is, how best or otherwise the gender roles are being played. Although, there was a delineation in the gender roles for male and female members of the traditional societies, even when it comes to the kind of life-long training. Apart from the preparation of everyone in the traditional life as enculturated and acceptable members of the society, Taiwo in Kosemani & Okorosaye-Orubite (1995) maintains that education of both male and female was to prepare them for occupation and economic self-reliance; in accordance with the traditions of the society they belong. One good thing about the characteristics of African indigenous education is that no gender, whether male or female was left behind in the traditional orientation and education; despite noticeable differentiation in gender roles. Provisions were made for boys and girls to become functional adults and economic enhancers, in their respective and peculiar ways.

Formal education also has characteristics of gender inclusivity, as it embraces both sexes as its receivers, particularly now that the world has recognized women as partners in development. Governments – at local and international levels have taken seriously the education of girls/women which culturally in Africa was *ab initio* trivialized. There are now advocacies and protocols that have been evolved at the intra and international levels, addressing women issues and concerns. For examples, affirmative actions are being pursued internally within countries, with demands for certain percentage of concession that favours women’s involvement in political participation and in other socio-economic sectors, believing in themselves as the vanguard and drivers to the development of their environment. For instance, the National Gender Policy (NGP) has formulated a 35% Affirmative Action (AA) in Nigeria since 2006. This policy demands that 35% of women be involved in all governance processes. The NGP is recognized, but not fully adhered to; as the structures and processes to use are not in place (Alliances for Africa, 2022). On the other hand, the old rhetoric of men’s world seems to be drawing back many women from presenting themselves for appointable positions or give men challenges for opportunities.

The matters concerning women have become of global concerns, that many countries now propitiate through one policy or the other, to address the peculiar situations of women and girls. From the continent, just as it is in Nigeria, Senegal also came up with gender parity law in 2010, with the provision for gender quota of 50/50. The law, according to Alliances for Africa (2022) obliges all political parties to nominate an equal number of women and men on party lists and as constituency candidates. With this law in place, parties are prevented from contesting elective positions without

complying with gender parity on candidates' lists. Following the implementation of the law, the year 2012 turned out to be remarkable for women political participation in Senegal with the number of women climbing 42.7% from the initial 22.7% level of political involvement.

Also, in Rwanda, women have been so mainstreamed that in the political space, the situation is now about equality; because there is a legislation that has made it mandatory for 30 percent of all representatives, including those in parliament to be women (Alliances for Africa, n.d.). To this extent, Alliances for Africa (2022) clarifies that Rwanda has quota for women, not just a quota solely on candidates, but rather reserves a minimum number of seats for women (often known as Equality of Result quotas). Only women are eligible to contest election for the women-only seats 7 (Alliances for Africa, n.d.).

From the foregoing, therefore, the opportunities for political participation and contributions of women to the economic growth of any society in this 21st century cannot be possible without being literate or sufficiently educated. What this means is that an educated woman can impact on the society in whatever capacities, even as a mother, wife, trader, administrator, or career woman.

The significance of education cannot be overemphasized, considering its need for women. Education is an instrument for change, women contribute immensely towards socio-economic development of any nation. Women form majority of the labour force doing what sustains life, growing food, cooking, managing the house and raising the children. Women have the potentials to stabilize a dwindling economy through their ability to plan and organize. This can only be possible if adequate attention is given to women education, irrespective of culture and religious background. No wonder Izuagba, Obilor & Obasi (2017) maintain that education is the only means through which people can be liberated from chronic poverty. The opportunity accorded women to have formal education has started yielding results, as a substantial number of women have become agents of change and development in the respective localities, even the country at large.

The major approach adopted in this work is the contextual explanations, expected to provide insight into the significance of educating women and its implications for the development of any nation. The study is therefore designed, first, to clarify the purpose of education and its developmental connections in the context of what education can do in the lives of women for their relevance and recognition; and to appraise the educated women's efforts which are channeled into changing the fortunes of Nigerian girls and women, as well as their contributions to national development.

Education for Development

If formal education offers to the individuals and the society what make them become useful, and the same education is ancillary to societal development; the purpose of education, therefore, is for development which many scholarly definitions corroborate. In this case, formal education "is the specialized training given in an organized manner with the basic aim of equipping the individual with the knowledge of reading, writing and calculation as well as specialized skills of interest and ability" (Okeke, 2016). According to her, the acquisition of this, gives individuals the enablement to be functional in the society. Okeke further delved into functionalist theory of education which is of the view that education is one of the institutions established to contribute

towards the survival and maintenance of the society, therefore, it is aimed at providing leadership in the teaching and acquisition of knowledge and skill required for the right functioning of societal members.

It is believed that education is an antidote to poverty and ignorance, a channel to individual's consciousness, an economic bulldozer and the life wire of every nation. This is not far from the position of Fafunwa (1974:17), who believes that "education is a process by which a child or young adult develops attitudes, abilities, skills and other forms of behaviours which are of positive values to the society in which he lives". On the other hand, Ayebe (2011) defines education as a process of imparting skills, attitudes, knowledge and values.

Education is the primary tool for nation building, Izuagba, Obilor & Obasi (2017) see it as the only instrument which can equip individuals with knowledge and skills to increase their productivity and as a result, liberate people from chronic poverty.

Development

Traditionally, people always look out for gigantic structures or buildings, flashy moving vehicles, good roads and so on; whenever we talk about development. For this reason, Ezeani (2005) states that the concept of development has eluded the Nigerian society. Robust facilities, glittering structures and landed properties are not what development portrays rather it only indicates its external perception. Experience has shown that there are various perceptions of development, a common feature of the various perceptions is that it involves changes, growth and deviation from what is considered normal or abnormal (Elems-Ikwegbu, 2024). The concept of development gives us a clearer understanding of the causes and solutions to problems, it also gets us well equipped to tackle it from the various perspectives. Generally, development is a change in manner or character of an individual or a change in a system, it can be measured in form of quality or quantity (Elems-Ikwegbu, 2024). Development involves the level of growth and improvement of activities in any given task.

However, Rodney (2009) sees development in human society as a many-sided process and from different perspectives. At the individual level, Rodney defines development as an increased skill and capacity, greater freedom, creativity, self-discipline, responsibility and material well-being which leads the individual to a greater freedom (Rodney, 2009; Elems-Ikwegbu, 2024). This level of development does not pass through a rigorous process, it can occur systematically or spontaneously, it includes one's ability to differentiate between right and wrong, Rodney further asserts that individual or personal development is tied with the state of the society. Therefore, at the societal level, he affirms that man elevated from hunting alone to forming a group and for the sake of survival, relationships were formed, these relationships resulted into social groups, so, at the societal level he sees development as an increasing capacity to regulate both internal and external relationships.

This is a clear indication that development can occur when an individual or group of individuals or a society moves from dependency to independency. All the same he sees development at the economic level as being dependent upon the individual members of the society. Economic and societal development cannot be experienced until the individual members of the society are developed. He further stresses that a society can only develop economically as members increase their capacity or device a means to deal with the environment, this depends on the extent to which they understand the

law of nature (science) and put the understanding into practice by devising tools (technology) and having the ability to carry out work in an organized manner.

Okafor & Okwarachukwu (2017) explain development as growth and improvement in individuals' ability and capacity for greater creativity, disciplines, responsibility and over all well-being, free from bondage and exploitation. Similarly, Nyerere in Duru & Opara (2017) sees development as the expansion of man's consciousness and the power over himself, his environment and the society. All the same, Ofuebe in Duru & Opara (2017), views development as "the ability of individual and society to interact with their physical, biological and the environment transforming them for their own betterment and in the process transfer the lessons that are learnt to future generation to enable them improve their capacity to make further valuable changes". However, Duru & Opara (2017) define development as "the improvement of all round well-being of people". Development can only take place when the people understand and appreciate the knowledge imparted in them and put them into practice to achieve a desirable improvement. Development can be quantitative or qualitative. Nevertheless, Amadi & Igbokwe (2017), define "development as the process of economic and social transformation that is based on complex cultural and environmental factors and their interactions". Udabah in Amadi & Igbokwe (2017) therefore portray development as improvement in living conditions.

National Development

National development has a strong bond with the concept of development, both are associated with growth, increase and change. National development is a general increase or positive change in a country's condition as a whole. Oke in Kingdom & Makae (2013:314), stresses that "national development is the ability of a nation to satisfactorily provide the food and fibre that are needed by its people and industry". It is imperative to mention that development, National development and education are connected, nevertheless; education is the only instrument that can equip individuals to climb the ladder to development. One thing is sure, the level of development aspired for, determines the level of educational pursuance. It has earlier been stated that education equips the individual to untie his creativity. Therefore, national development can only occur when there is enormous or significant improvement in the life styles of the citizens when they realize their talents and develop their potentials (Afinowi, 2022). A nation is a large community of people with diverse culture but share common interest and language. Nigeria is a nation, despite the cultural diversity, it shares binding principles and policies.

Issues and Concerns in the Education of Girls and Women in National Development

Identified below are the areas of concerns for which women are either being shortchanged, or not properly placed, to bring out their innate best and, are impeded in playing their roles for the development of the country. It is no doubt that efforts have been made by individuals, religious organizations, non-governmental organizations and the government to provide adequate and equal educational opportunities for girls/women. However, some factors are still hindering the achievement of holistic education and participation of women in societal/national affairs. These factors are as follow:

Family Economic Condition: The level of education of the young ones is always measured and determined by the economic situation of the immediate family. This is more noticeable in large families where funds are limited. According to Osokoya (2007), such family would prefer to enroll the boys instead of the girls. The girls are made to stay back at home and join their mothers in petty trading. These factors loom large especially in the rural areas.

Cultural/Religious Background: Culture in most cases interacts with religious beliefs or practices. On that note, Williams in Oniye & Okoro (2006) submits that the extent to which cultural and religious belief prohibits women playing a role outside the home can go a long way to hinder girls/women access to education. Girl child education is considered unimportant if women are confined only to domestic duties and offer for early marriages, as it is seen in the context of African practice. Similarly, Islamic religion clearly forbids girls from mixing with boys and as a result, Abdulrahman (2018) indicates that this has been misconstrued by many parents, leading to their apathy and resulting in low level of girl-children enrollment in schools, despite the fact that provisions are made for girls and boys to study in separate classrooms, as obvious in the northern Nigeria. Osokoya (2007:105) portrays the UNESCO's data on girls' enrollment in the northern part of Nigeria, indicating as low as 39%, 39%, 27% and 15% in Bauchi, Jigawa, Katsina and Sokoto States respectively in 2004. In spite of the enormous efforts that were made by government, religious organizations, individuals and non-governmental organizations, women literacy rate especially in the rural areas are still low, compared to that of their men counterpart.

Organization of School: Organization of schools is another factor that hinders women education. Parents who are under stringent religious and cultural policy may find it difficult to allow their female children to attend mixed schools. Such parents will prefer to keep their female children at home, rather than go against their religion or culture. This is common in the northern part of Nigeria where Islamic religion dominates the society and forbids indiscriminate mixing of opposite sex (Abdulrahman, 2018). The provision made by government and concerned individuals may not provide adequate access; as a result, good number of girls are automatically left out of this opportunity.

Level of Education of Parents: The level of parents' educational attainment especially the mothers speak volume in the education of the younger offspring. An educated woman might not pay attention to some insinuations that fly around the community such as: educated girls are morally corrupt, they are barren, will not accept parents' choice of husbands, will not be humble to their husbands, not have time for domestic duties, not marry and so on.

Labour Market Opportunities and Policy: Labour market opportunity and organizational policy are also hindering factors, mostly tied to religious and cultural attitudes. Time and dresses required for the work always remain an issue when it comes to women. They are expected to take lesser sophisticated jobs to enable them return home early to take care of their husbands and children. Also, the dress code of the job may not be acceptable by the immediate society or religion. In addition, some jobs are hazardous in nature and as such cannot be taken up by women, these job conditions have limited women's involvement in job participation.

Government Policy and Implementation: Government policy and implementation serve as a huge set back in Nigerian education system. It is no doubt that the policy makers are aware of cultural diversities and religious differences in Nigeria, yet one of

the goals of Nigerian education clearly states that “education is compulsory and the right of every Nigerian irrespective of gender, socio-status, religion, colour, ethnic background and any particular individual challenges (FRN, 2014; Bukar, 2025). Clearly, some of the factors that hinder women education are found in the aforementioned educational goal which adequate efforts have not been taken to arrest the situation.

Appraisal in the Context of Women Education and National Development

In the context of magnifying women education and national development, the efforts are to engage in the appraisal of the dynamics in the issues of women and education; examining the religious characteristics, policy perspective, participation in and women’s contributions to national development; with reminiscence on Nigeria.

Perspective of Religion and Women’s Status in Development

From the angle of religion, contrary to the erroneous quotes, peddled and popularized about women’s subjugation and subservience in Islam, it should be known that the main aim of Islamic education is not far from those characterized in the two other systems of education, African Traditional/Indigenous Education and Formal Western Education, that is; to intellectually, socially, economically and culturally develop every member of the society, male and female, consequently developing their society. Abdulrahman (2018:339) affirms that:

“...the Holy Qur’an indicates and places emphasis on the pursuit or acquisition of knowledge by all Muslims, irrespective of their sexes and that God commands both male and female to read, recite, think and contemplate as well as learn from the signs - the “Ayat” of Allah”.

Apparently from the foregoing, Islam as a religion does not restrict or prohibit women and girls from seeking knowledge or get trained and be formally or informally educated. In the life-time of Prophet Muhammed (may the peace of God be upon him), women were accorded pride of place and were permitted to attend scholarly gatherings, even encouraged to ask questions on any ambiguities. Also, in the early period of Islam in Nigeria; particularly in the time of Sheik Uthman Dan Fodio, he used to allow women amidst the gathering for knowledge acquisition or his preaching. *Sheik Uthman Dan Fodyio* was an Islamic reformer, educationist and gender advocate who did not only fight for Islamic cause, but saw education as an indispensable weapon to fight ignorance, poverty and tyranny. Dan Fodyio’s educational priority was significantly extended to the women and girls.

Fafunwa (1974: 49-50) corroboratively reports that the most outstanding reforms by Dan-Fodyio was the education of women which in his book – *Nur al-Albab*, wherein, Dan Fodyio says “they treat their wives and daughters like household implements which are used until they are broken and then thrown on to the rubbish heap. Alas! How can they abandon their wives and daughters in the perpetual darkness of ignorance while they daily impart their knowledge to their students in this manner out of sheer egotism and hypocrisy?” (Mejiuni, 2013)

In addition, the need for educating women was also contained in another Fodyio’s work titled *Ihya al Sunnah*. Among the Hausas and Fulanis of Nigeria, Uthman Dan Fodyio was the first to practically demonstrate the positive disposition of Islam to knowledge; as exemplified by the Holy Qur’an. Fodyio’s practical demonstration of

this, thereafter gave many of the northern aristocrats the impetuses to seek modern education as well as extending same to their children. Abdulrahman (2010) even revealed that the two daughters of Sheik Dan Fodyio were scholars of repute in the history of Islam in the Hausa land and Nigeria. Also, it was reported by Fafunwa (1974) and Kosemani & Okorosaye-Orubite (2002) that the elder sister was a teacher and scholar, providing instruction and teaching lessons on Islamic studies, law and Islamic jurisprudence (fiqh). On the other hand, the younger sister, Asmau Nana was a renowned poet, with large volumes of poems composed and documented for use among Muslims and lovers of knowledge.

In the Christendom, there is no much of indictment or controversy in the education of women or girls as does being misrepresented in Islam. In the Holy Bible, it is very crystally clear that we shall account for how a shepherd direct his flocks. Metaphorically in this context, our women and girls are referred here as the flocks. Failure of men and the societies to provide opportunities for the girls and women to be educated is one thing that God has warned. On the other hand, women are also warned to be obedient to their husbands, and wife not to be barred by the husband from seeking knowledge. Corroborative of this; Ephesians 5:22-33 urges wives "...be submissive to your own husband as unto the Lord. For the husbands is the head of the wife, just as Christ is the head and saviour of the church, which is His body. But as the church submits to Christ, so also let the wives be to their own husbands in everything". It is also very clear that Christianity did not make any categorical statement against women being educated, but the emphasis is on the obedience to the husband which does not interpret to mean that husbands should restraint their wives from being educated. The only caution which has to be recognized is just that the wives should respect and be obedient to their husbands.

Importantly, women are to be well trained and educated for the good of their homes and society, and be instrumental to the growth of another woman. In Titus 2:4-8, the Bible says: "...these older women must train the younger women to love their husbands and their children, to live wisely and be pure, to work in their homes, to do good, and to be submissive to their husbands. Then, they will not bring shame on the word of God".

Also, women education occupies a pride of place in Christianity, whereby older women are encouraged to prioritize the training of younger women, for the best to be seen in them as wives or mothers. Note that it would not have become a need for the Bible to encourage the older women to train the younger ones, if knowledge among women is unnecessary. There is therefore, the recognition of the fact that women must be equipped with the knowledge, skills and how to perfectly play their role to bring their worth and be impactful on the family and societal development.

Considering the above scriptural accounts, it must therefore be mentioned that there should be no discrimination in the attainment of education, because of religion or cultural beliefs. Today, women who missed out of formal schooling or did not have the opportunity to attend formal schools are being provided opportunities by government, religious organizations, non-governmental organizations and some wealthy individuals through the means of adult and non-formal education. The low level of girl child enrollment which existed in some parts of Nigeria could be attributed to religious misconception or cultural characteristics which mixing of both boys and girls is given as excuse, even when girls only schools are everywhere (Maigida, 2018).

In view of the above, there is no excuse for this again, as all these are being attended to. Governments have begun the establishment of only female and only male schools, particularly the Federal Government; even at the tertiary level which might have been seen by people to be impossible in a country like Nigeria. There is now the provision of separate schools/colleges for girls and boys. In Abdulrahman (2023), it was revealed that all states of the federation have; in addition to the mixed unity school (Federal Government College) in each state of the federation, so also are the girls only unity schools in all the states in Nigeria. In addition to this, a Federal College of Education (women only) has been established in Zamfara State (Abdulrahman, 2023).

Policy and Legal Perspectives

As part of the fundamental human rights, contained in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Chapter IV: 34 – right to dignity of human person and 42 - right to freedom from discrimination, including right to education (FRN, 1999). The UBE Act, 2004 also provides for compulsory education for all, irrespective of gender, conceived as Basic Education which is compulsory, free and Universal.

In the colonial Nigeria, the report of Phelps Stoke’s commission submitted in 1922 strongly prioritized the education of girls and it was eventually captured in the 1926 Education Ordinance. Consequently, this report culminated in the establishment of the very first Nigerian government secondary school for the girls in 1927, that is, the Queen’s College, Lagos. In the post-independence Nigeria, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) provides that “education is compulsory and a right for every Nigerian citizen, *irrespective of gender*, social status, religion, colour, ethnic background and any peculiar individual challenges. However, the implementation of this policy provision has to be strengthened, as there are still situations or practices, though cultural, where women are subjugated and confined to household or domestic chores and raising children; without the opportunity provided for self-development, particularly to get educated” (Hambeh, 1985). In some parts of Nigeria, women are at the receiving end of whatever happens, mostly in the negative side; even blamed for everything wrong in the family.

In marriages, some women are meted with rejection and divorce for lack of male child/children – a situation which is not their own making. African tradition allows man to take as many wives as possible; the reason behind this is procreation for large number of children, but strongly believed by cultural practice, not to be achievable with one or two wives. In the same vein, the cultural reason for many wives may also be because of bearing only female children by a wife. Traditionally, the worth of women was not so valued, that male children are always desired. Attention is therefore accorded male children, to the detriment of the girls who are potential nation builders and architect of development. It is good to note that there are strong regulations and advocacies against inhuman treatments of girls and women, even many instruments, organisations and agencies in the women’s rights protection against domestic violence, rape, trafficking, child-labour, and other obnoxious cultural practices and exploitations, including luring girls into prostitution.

Women’s Participation in National Development

In the contribution of women to national development, first of all, women are naturally and specially gifted with lots of talents. As a matter of fact, they are better natural resources manager and economic enhancers. For the best they can offer to be

manifested, all that is required for them is to be well educated, and when they are, this will no doubt bring them to the right track and consequently facilitate a quick turnaround in the Nigerian economy. Generally, what is seen as the primary assignment of women in Africa is centered on household chores/raising children. Even if these are the main tasks of women, the question may be asked, thus; what will be the level of intellectual capability of children raised by an uneducated woman? The answer to this cannot be far-fetched, as the woman who is not educated can only give what she has. Bearing in mind that children are seen as the leaders of tomorrow, the ripple effect or the consequence of raising a child by an uneducated woman or mother is that the tomorrow holds no promise for a better society.

Woman needs to be equipped with the capability to exhibit their innate and endowed potentials before she can discover her children's talents or potentials, and supporting them to nurse their creativity which will prove them to be functional adults in the society and leading to improved national development.

Education provides women with the basic knowledge and skills which make them the change agents for a dynamic society. As earlier stated, religion and cultural variations continue to hinder the expected growth, transformation and development of women and girls in Nigeria. Most at times, some women find it difficult to decipher how to overcome difficult situations when faced with one, this is due to poor level of educational attainment. Education and development have been noted by many scholars as "two sides of a coin", they are inseparable.

Some organizations have emerged to bring out the potentials and creativity in Nigerian women and to change their lives for the growth and development of the nation. Afinowi, (2022) provides some leading organizations that are aimed at changing the lives of Nigerian women and girls. To mention but a few are as follows:

- **Awesome Treasures Foundation:** founded by Jumoke Adenowo. It is a faith-based organization supporting the overall growth and development of women. It connects women with one another and help them find their purposes in life.
- **Kind Nigeria:** Founded by Haffat Abiola-Castello, the Kudirat Initiative for Democracy which promotes leadership development for young women and remove barriers to women's public participation and seeks to end violence against women.
- **Moremi Initiative:** founded in 2011 and led by Olufunke Baruwa with the aim to increase the representation of women in governance and seeks to address gender imbalance in elective and appointive positions.
- **She Leads Africa:** founded by Yasmin Belo-Osagie and Afua Osei. It is dedicated to empowering the next generation of African women entrepreneurs, it seeks to drive Africa's growth which Nigeria is inclusive through leadership, commerce and innovation.
- **WAAW Foundation:** founded by Unoma Okoroafor. It is on a mission to encourage and empower girls in the field of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) (The Guardian Nigeria, n.d.).

From the religious angle, there are many formal Christian societies within the church bodies and many others outside the church, providing supportive and charity works which are mainly for women's upliftment and empowerment. For instance, there are a number of such, not limited to Catholic Women Organisation, Anglican Women Society, Methodist Women Society, as well as those of the various Pentecostal

churches doing everything humanly possible to add values to the status of women, including their education, empowerment and promoting their sustainable livelihood (Abdulrahman, 2022). Also, in the Islamic religion, education has been given pride of place for both sexes. More importance is now being accorded women and girls education. Today, a number of Muslim individuals and Islamic organizations have come to recognize the need to get women and girls educated. As provided by Abdulrahman (2018:339), these organisations are: Ansar-Ud-Deen and the Nasrul-lahi al-fathi society. Substantial number of women have excelled, even providing livelihood to many others, including men, because of what education has transformed them to become. Abdulrahman further provides that Ansar-Ud-Deen society promoted the non-stringent rules on the role of women in the community and rejected the seclusion of women. Even in the colonial Nigeria, Reichmuth in Abdulrahman (2018:339) “recounts that in the early years of Ansar Ud Deen, women played major roles in the financial solvency of the society and their contributions were noted in its first published newsletter in 1924”.

All these efforts have yielded positive results as substantial number of women now occupy political positions (ministerial, board and agencies) in Nigeria, even in the civil service, oil and financial (Banking & Businesses) industry, women are there as chief executive officers, irrespective of religion and cultural background.

Contributions of Educated Women to National Development

Women are agents of change, socio-economic and national development. Every woman has potentials and talents and would stop at nothing to unleash them if given the opportunity. Their high level of educational attainment has helped them acquire adequate knowledge and skills and have contributed to national development in the following ways:

- **Raising Future Leaders:** As earlier mentioned, even though traditionally or primarily, women’s assignment rests on house-hold chores and raising children. It should as well be noted that these children are the future leaders, a woman can only give out what she has. In most cases, attention is channeled to the school alone, but we should not forget that the woman as a mother, will have to prepare the child’s mind prior to his enrollment into the school, only an educated woman can see the importance of early child hood care, development and education as the foundation of learning which the child should not miss. According to Fatunwa (1974), the education of the child in Nigerian society starts from infancy. At this stage, the child is glued to the mother and learnt from her first; before interacting with other members of the family and the society. This stage is very crucial in the life of every individual child, the mother’s educational attainment goes a long way to influence the child’s behaviour when he eventually mixes up with other children and members of the immediate environment and finally finds himself in school. Besides, the dynamic society also requires the mother to pay adequate attention to the child’s academic performance in school.

With these tasks, the children of educated women are always outstanding among their peers in every aspect of life. They provide equal educational opportunities for their children irrespective of their sexes. Levine in Osokoya (2007:107-108) argues that educated women would be more able to prepare their children for participation in the new socio-economic order than the uneducated women. Education does not only

prepare a woman to participate in societal and national development, it also enables her prepare her offspring for leadership participation (Osokoya, 2007).

- **Adding to National Values:** Women constitute about half of the entire population, those that received Western and Islamic education in the early years did not sweep their knowledge under the carpet, they came together and formed numerous organizations to create awareness in the minds of women and to clear them of every naivety. Few of the organizations have been mentioned earlier in this discourse, lots of achievements were recorded.

In addition to the organizations earlier mentioned, many known Nigerian women and ladies have been notable beneficiaries of what the society offers as fortunes and they were champions involved in promoting the cause of women and girls. These women were able to launch themselves into limelight, not because of anything that is far-fetched, but for being educated which is aiding their recognition, appointment or engagement for local, national and international assignments, thus:

Table 1. Notable Nigerian Women of Excellence in the Public Affairs

Name	Position/Status	Name	Position/Status
Amina Mohammed	<i>Deputy UN Secretary General</i>	Dr. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala	<i>Former Minister of Finance</i>
Prof. Ruqqayatu Ahmed Rufa'i	<i>Former Minister of Education</i>	Mrs. Amma Pepple	<i>Former Minister, Land Housing & Urban Development</i>
Prof. Dora Akunyili	<i>Former Director General, NAFDAC</i>	Dr. Sarah Jibril	<i>Former Presidential Aspirant and renowned politician</i>
Florence Ita-Giwa	<i>Senator of the Federal Republic of Nigeria</i>	Princess Stella Oduah	<i>Former Minister of Aviation & Nigerian Senator</i>
Omobola Johnson Olubusola	<i>Former Minister of Communication Technology</i>	Sarah Reng Ochekepe	<i>Former Minister of Water Resources</i>
Prof. Viola Onwuliri	<i>Former Minister of State for Foreign Affairs</i>	Erelu Olusola Bada	<i>Former Minister of State Defence</i>
Hadiza Ibrahim Mailafia	<i>Former Minister of Environment</i>	Moji Makanjuola	<i>Veteran Journalist & Ace Broadcaster</i>
Abike Dabiri-Erewa	<i>Celebrated Journalist & now Director, NIDCOM</i>	Oloye Olajumoke Akinjide	<i>Former Minister of State for FCT</i>
Hajia Zainab Maina	<i>Former Minister of Women Affairs</i>	Pauline Tallen	<i>Former Minister of Women Affairs</i>
Hadiza Bala Usman	<i>Former Managing Director, Nigerian Ports Authority</i>	Kofoworola Bucknor-Akerele	<i>Former Deputy Governor of Lagos State under Governor Tinubu</i>
Gbemisola Saraki	<i>Senator and former Minister, Federal Republic of Nigeria.</i>	Sinatu Aderoju Ojikutu	<i>Former Deputy Governor of Lagos State under Governor Otedola</i>
Halimat Yusuf	<i>Former Minister</i>	Prof. Salami	<i>VC, UNIBEN</i>
Prof. Florence Banku-Obi	<i>First female VC, UNICAL</i>	Prof. Folasade Tolulope Ogunsola	<i>VC, UNILAG</i>
Prof. Bidemi Bilkis Lafiaji-Okuneye	<i>VC, LASUED</i>	Dr. Temitope Ilori	<i>DG (NACA)</i>

Prof. Medinat Folorunsho Salman	<i>KWASUED, Ilorin.</i>	Prof. Nnenna Nnannaya Oti	<i>VC, FUTO, Owerri</i>
Obiageli Katryn Ezekwesili	<i>Former Nigerian Education Minister & Former Vice President of the World Bank</i>	Hadiza Bala Usman	<i>Former Managing Director, Nigerian Ports Authority</i>

Source: Author's compilation, 2024.

It is obvious that the total number of women in leadership position does not in any way match with the number of men. However, there is now a progress, resulting from the societal acceptance and positive consideration of women to a large extent in the scheme of things. They breaking the glass ceilings and a booster for many other women to be courageous and strive to launch themselves to stardom. If women therefore, have more representation in leadership and other formal positions, substantial value would be added to their immediate society and the nation would become better for it. This, therefore, requires that they have equal access to formal and non-formal education and equal opportunity to enable them contribute their quota and have their inputs in the socio-economic and political development of the society.

The Narratives about the First Ladies' Developmental Contributions

In Nigeria, the position of first lady has generated a narrative that should receive commendations and not condemnation; when it comes to the matter of womenfolk in Nigeria. Since the country began to officially recognize first ladies in political landscape in Nigeria, that is, the wife of the president or the governor, as it is a tradition in the American practice which many governments of the world now replicate. The office has been characterized with one special (pet) project or the other, as the first ladies' contributions to the development of the individuals, consequently the development of the society. when touching on the lives of the people positively through diverse interventions, but targeted more on matters relating to women/girls and children, and other vulnerable groups.

Table 210 First Ladies in the Nigerian History and their Developmental Programmes/Pet Projects

First Ladies	Developmental Programmes/Pet Projects
<i>Mrs. Maryam Babangida</i>	<i>Better Life Programme (BLP)</i>
In the history of Nigerian politics, the country saw the birth of Better Life Programme (BLP) in September 1987; conceived as a strategy to mainstream and close gender-gap, ultimately for socio-economic and political empowerment of Nigerian women, mostly in the rural areas. BLP was the brain child and pet project of late Mrs. Maryam Babangida, wife of the former Head of State - General Ibrahim Babangida (retired) (Ihimodu, 1996).	
<i>Mrs. Maryam Abacha</i>	<i>Family Support Programme (FSP)</i>
Another known first lady project that followed was the Family Support Programme (FSP) of the former first lady and wife of late General Sanni Abacha, Mrs. Maryam Abacha, which was launched in November 1993; to address the welfare of vulnerable groups, particularly women and children, for the improvement of the targets' social and economic well-being.	
<i>Justice Fati Lami Abubakar</i>	<i>Women's Rights Advancement and Protection (WRAPA)</i>
Justice Fati launched her own Pet Project tagged Women's Rights Advancement and Protection (WRAPA) in June 1998, for advancement and protection of women and girls' rights, focusing on array of issues on gender equality, legal advocacy and social justice.	

<i>Mrs. Stela Obasanjo</i>	<i>Child Care Trust (CCT)</i>
The return to civilian rule and evolution of democratic governance in 1999 gave birth to the Child Care Trust (CCT) in May 1999 with its motto ‘Sowing the Seeds of Hope’ as the Pet Project of the then first lady and wife of Chief Olusegun Obasanjo, Late Mrs. Stela Obasanjo; targeting the children and women with any form of challenges or disabilities.	
<i>Mrs. Turai Yar’Adua</i>	<i>Women and Youth Empowerment Foundation (WAYEF)</i>
Late President Umaru Musa Yar’Adua succeeded President Obasanjo and the then first lady Mrs. Turai Yar’Adua, wife of President Umaru Musa Yar’Adua, had her own pet project as Women and Youth Empowerment Foundation (WAYEF), launched in May 2007; targeted on health, poverty reduction, drug abuse and lifelong education.	
<i>Mrs. Patience Jonathan</i>	<i>Areuera Reachout Foundation (ARF)</i>
“Mama Peace” as fondly called - Mrs. Patience Jonathan, the wife of former President Goodluck Jonathan had her pet project Areuera Reachout Foundation (ARF) since she was a first lady in Bayelsa State. ARF according to Ezeobi & Ejifoma (2020) was to provide training for women, medical support and assistance to people with heart conditions, empowering the youths and women to overcome challenges through skills acquisition and development for productivity and wealth creation as well as rehabilitation of female ex-convicts especially in the Niger Delta. It also extended its mission of reaching out to the elderly.	
<i>Mrs. Aisha Buhari</i>	<i>Future Assured (FA)</i>
The immediate past administration of President Muhammadu Buhari produced Future Assured (FA) as the pet project of the then first lady - Mrs. Aisha Buhari, wife of the former President Muhammadu Buhari. Future Assured is an initiative of the Aisha Buhari Foundation (ABF), a Non-Governmental Organisation with widespread advocacy for the wellbeing of women, children and adolescents in Nigeria, started in May 2015 (ThisDay Live, 2020).	
<i>Senator Oluremi Tinubu</i>	<i>Renewed Hope Initiative (RHI)</i>
In the current dispensation, beginning in 2023; the wife of President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria - Senator Oluremi Tinubu as a trained and professional educator/teacher also toed the lines of her predecessors. In her career record, she worked with the Department of Science and Technology Education, University of Lagos before delving into politics. Being the Nigeria’s first lady now, her experience as an educator has become an asset in her political career as she is using her expertise in advocating for women’s education and empowerment (TheWill Newspaper, 2023). It is the characteristic of anyone in the position of first lady, to initiate a (pet) project or programme for the benefit of girls and women. As somebody who believes in investing in society’s human capital, the current Nigerian first lady – Senator Oluremi Tinubu has launched the Renewed Hope Initiative (RHI), from her husband developmental conceptions for the transformation of Nigeria; focusing on agriculture, health, education, social investment and economic empowerment across the 36 states of the federation and the Federal Capital Territory (TheWill Newspaper, 2023).	

Source: Author’s compilation, 2024.

Other first ladies, their personalities, education and activities are as presented in the appendix: ***See Appendix One.***

In short, Appendix One reveals that women have come to the realization that education is needed to get them out of the cocoon and sprout with remarkable launch into limelight, particularly in the political space. Not much would have been obvious to talk about in terms of women as agents of development, if education does not feature. To be educated is now a priority, as impressively revealed in the efforts of the wives of the Governors (First Ladies) in Nigeria. Launching themselves into limelight through education has equally afforded them the chance to carry many women and girls along. This can be seen from the various pet projects and many of the well-articulated programmes embarked upon, reflected as demonstrated; including marvelous activities of the established Non-Governmental Organisations/Foundations where girls’ education, women empowerment for sustainable livelihood are outstandingly provided.

Conclusion

It is crystal clear that education of women and girls is instrumental to socio-economic, political and other areas of measuring national development. Despite plethora of bottlenecks and perceived inequality that are believed to be hindering women education and their participation in the social and political affairs, there are manifesting improvements on disparity in education, irrespective of religion and culture. Efforts made by the government, non-governmental organizations, religious group and some concerned individuals, including all the Nigerian first ladies, prioritizing concerns for the womenfolk; all of these efforts have therefore started yielded positive results, as substantial number of women have developed self-consciousness and embraced education for a better future for themselves and the development of the country.

Suggestions

As revealed in the findings and the discussions so far, the researchers suggest that in spite of the encouraging intervention gradually changing the fortunes of the female gender; extra attention is needed in the aforementioned challenging areas to make way for excellent results in women educational attainment, consequently spurring further development of Nigeria. In addition to the foregoing, the following shall equally be very important to note, thus:

- More of carefully planned separate schools be provided to make ways for girls and women whose culture/religion forbids indiscriminate mixing of the opposite sexes. This will defeat the excuse of some parents for not sending their girl-children to school. Doing this on the other hand, it amounts to respecting the religious rights of every individual in their quest for livelihood supports and contribution to national development.
- Early marriage should be abolished, considering the challenges of our ever-changing society where many women are left stranded after losing their husbands untimely. Women should be well education to be assured of sustainable livelihood and bearing in mind that educated women reproduce better future leaders.
- More priority attention to be accorded girls and women in the educational access, motivation and opportunities. So also, implementation of the 35% affirmative action be sacrosanct.
- Government should provide conducive learning environment to accommodate every citizen, with drastic measures taken to curb higher level of youth restiveness, social vices and all sorts of immoral acts that engulf public schools, especially at the higher level.

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Appendix One

Some Nigerian Governors' Wives (First Ladies), Education and the Developmental Inputs

S/N	Name & State	Academic/Education	Activities/project
1.	Her Excellency, Hajiya Lami Fintiri – Adamawa State	A holder of Pre-Degree (Diploma), UNIMAID and a Degree from Moddibo Adama University of Technology, Yola	Her determination and commitment to the well-being and empowerment of women and youths led to the establishment of Fresh Air Pro-Life Empowerment Foundation, a Non-Governmental Organisation that provides skills, enlightenment for women and youths of Adamawa State. The first lady is also an advocate of girl-child education. Her NGO has organised different training programmes in computer innovation, awareness of sexual violence and the importance of girl-child education.
2.	Her Excellency, Mrs. Priscilla Otti - Abia State	Graduate of Economics from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka	The First lady is passionate about human rights, child care and women empowerment. She has been devoting her office and time to pursue a better life for women and children in her state.
3.	Her Excellency, Mrs. Nkechinyere Mbah - Enugu State	A holder of Bachelor's Degree in Biotechnology, Federal University of Technology, Imo State, Nigeria, a professional certification in Women Entrepreneurship and Leadership for Africa, from the China Europe International Business School, Pudong, Shanghai, in collaboration with Harvard University.	Mrs Mbah is one of the founders and facilitators of the Peter Mbah Foundation, a Charity Organisation geared towards grassroots empowerment and development for communities, women and children. She is passionate about grassroots empowerment and development for communities.
4.	Her Excellency, Mrs. Patience Eno - Akwa Ibom State	Well educated, but now late. May her soul rest in peace.	Mrs Eno has embraced her husband's A.R.I.S.E vision as her pet project. The A.R.I.S.E agenda focuses on Agricultural revolution, Rural development, Infrastructural maintenance/ advancement, Security management and educational advancement among women, children and the underprivileged in Akwa Ibom. The First lady chose the feminine aspect of the A.R.I.S.E agenda and has impacted the lives of widows, orphans and the less privileged in the state.
5.	Her Excellency, Eyoanwan Bassey-Otu - Cross River State.	She attended the then Cross River State Polytechnic (now, Cross River State University) and later B.Sc. & Master in Public Admin. A career teacher, started at the Holy Child Secondary School in Calabar	concentrating on women, widows, the girl child and the people living with disabilities in Cross River

6.	Her Excellency, Tobore Oborevwo - Delta State.	A graduate of Sociology. She attended St. Ita's Girls Grammar School, Sapele, and later on, the Delta State University Abraka, for her bachelor's degree in Sociology.	As her pet project, she has embraced the MORE agenda of her husband, focusing on Meaningful development, Opportunities for all, Realistic reforms, Enhanced peace and security , but interested in the aspect that deals with women and children. She has provided succour for petty traders and enhanced small and medium businesses across the state.
7.	Her Excellency, Hajiya Asma'u Inuwa Yahaya - Gombe State.	A Computer Scientist. Graduate of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU), Bauchi.	An advocate of good governance, girl-child education and women empowerment, she established Jewel Care Foundation, a Non-Governmental Organisation (Jewel Care) where children, women and the underprivileged find succour. As part of her initiative, she has established breast and cervical screening centres across the state. A lot of women and students have also benefited from her free distribution of sanitary towels and hygiene packs.
8.	Her Excellency, Hajiya Zulaihat & Fatima Dikko Radda - Katsina State.	Zulaihat Diploma in law BUK, Advanced Diploma in Public Admin. Later, she had her B. Sc. in Political Sci and eventually bagged a Master's degree in Public Admin at University of Abuja. In the case of Hajia Fatima, she is graduate of the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria	They empowered several women, youths and start-ups with capital for small and medium businesses across the 34 local Government Areas in the state. Through her Foundation, Pledging Aid Charity Foundation (PAC-F) they are also concerned about fighting sexual violence and the rate of infant mortality in the state; working to ensure the number is reduced
9.	Her Excellency, Dr. Ibijoke Babajide Sanwo-Olu - Lagos State	A medical doctor by profession. She has two Master's degrees in Business Administration and Public Health	The First lady, through her office, has supported her husband's T.H.E.M.E.S Agenda. The overall goal is to bring strategic development to Lagos State through traffic management and transportation; health and environment; education and technology; entertainment and tourism; as well as security and governance, all geared toward making Lagos a 21st Century economy. In the health sector, she has revived, rejuvenated and repositioned the health sector for optimal service delivery. She also set up 'Adopt-A-Child Project', an initiative to help parents who cannot afford to give their children quality education. Many children have been taken off the streets and back to school after getting scholarships from the First lady. The fight to eradicate Sexual and Gender-Based Violence (SGBV) from the state is another area that she has invested in. Pep talks, enlightenment campaigns and counseling have provided for victims of SGBV.
10.	Her Excellency, Silifat A Sule – Nasarawa State.	Silifat attended Ahmadu Bello University where she bagged a degree in Food and Nutrition.	She has established the Silifat A. Sule Hope Foundation, SAS, an NGO aimed at providing humanitarian programmes for women, children and youths. SAS has touched many lives through skills acquisition, soft loan provision, payment of medical bills, provision of 'Mama's Kit', an ante natal kit

			for pregnant women, in order to encourage them to go for treatment duration pregnancy. Many children have also been taken off the streets and they are enjoying scholarships in various schools.
11.	Her Excellency, Bamidele Abiodun - Ogun State.	Graduate of Zoology, University of Ibadan.	She has initiated several programmes with a focus on social welfare, health, education and poverty reduction. One of the programmes she has created is 'She Venture,' in collaboration with First City Monument Bank (FCMB). It is an initiative focused on boosting the economic capacity of women by offering both financial and non-financial support to small and medium scale businesses owned by women.
12.	Her Excellency, Engr. Tamunominini Olufunke Makinde - Oyo State	A Nigerian trained Petrochemical engineer, described brilliant and educated first lady. She studied engineering in her first degree and crowned it with double first class honours - BBA & MBA (Business Administration) from St. Thomas University at Houston, Texas in the US.	passionate about improving the welfare of women and children in the state. She chose women empowerment as her pet project, starting different empowerment schemes that have provided soft loans and grants to traders and business women. The First lady has also done a lot through her office to raise awareness of violence against women and children and child trafficking. By embarking on a massive enlightenment campaign, she has been able to help curtail the menace in parts of the state.
13.	Her Excellency, Nonye Soludo - Anambra State	First degree in Computer Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka and a Master's degree in Accounting & Finance, University of Westminster, United Kingdom.	Being a fitness, healthy living enthusiast, she established a scheme known as the Healthy Living with Nonye Soludo across schools in Anambra State. In addition to this initiative, she has improved the lives of many widows, women and underprivileged in the state.
14.	Her Excellency, Aishatu Bala – Bauchi State.	She has a first degree in Public Administration at the University of Abuja and has taken many more educational courses thereafter.	She was married off after primary education, spurring her focus for girl child education. Therefore, she established Al-Muhibbah Foundation, a Non-Governmental Organisation committed to educating the girl-child and raising awareness about the disadvantages of early marriage. The NGO has also helped the vulnerable and less privileged in the state
15.	Her Excellency, Gloria Diri – Bayelsa State	Graduate of Nursing. A matron before her role as first lady.	With her foundation, Gloria Diri Foundation; a large number of people in Bayelsa, including the elderly have substantially benefitted. Also, Mrs Diri is a strong advocate against teenage pregnancy and drug abuse.
16.	Her Excellency, Betty Obaseki – Edo State.	Bachelor and Master's degrees in Accounting in Nigeria and overseas. She also has a Master's degree in International Law, an alumnus of the Kellogg's School of Business Executive Management Program, North Western	She has empowered a lot of women, advocated and fought against sexual violence in the state, giving her recognition for her contribution in this regard. She is passionate about girl child, leading to the introduction of: (1) Junior Achievement of Nigeria, whose goal is to educate young people on various social and environmental issues and a non-profit organization (2) Ladies Aware, which

		University in Illinois, United States	empowers young ladies with skills and creates awareness for ladies about their rights.
17.	Her Excellency, Biodun Abayomi Oyebanji – Ekiti State	Graduate of the University of Ibadan in 1997 with a lecturing career starting at Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti in the year 2000 as a research fellow in the Department of Education. Lecturing in her alma mater, University of Ibadan before resuming as first lady	is focusing on gender advocacy by raising her voice against gender-based violence in the state. She also established the Biodun Abayomi Oyebanji Foundation, BAO in Ekiti state where the aged, widows and less privileged women are taken care of.
18.	Her Excellency, Chioma Uzodinma – Imo State.	a graduate of Law from Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State.	Barrister Uzodinma has showcased an impeccable profile of mother to all in the state and she has given succour, hope and happiness through the Good Hope Flourish Foundation, an initiative that has empowered women and children in Imo state. Apart from her passion for the vulnerable

Source: Authors' Adapted (2024) & Wesley-Metibogun (2023). First ladies and their pet projects. THEWILL

